

Price change effects on government tax revenue in Nigeria

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17088432>

Abstract

This study examined the effects of price changes, specifically inflation rates, exchange rates, and crude oil prices, on government tax revenues in Nigeria. The findings revealed that variations in inflation rates did not significantly affect tax revenue, suggesting that short-term inflationary pressures have a limited influence on fiscal outcomes. In contrast, exchange rate fluctuations had a notable impact on tax revenue, as currency depreciation changes the local currency value of traded goods, exports, and imports, thereby affecting taxable income and customs duties. Similarly, changes in crude oil prices had a significant impact on government revenue, reflecting Nigeria's heavy reliance on oil-related fiscal inflows, including taxes, royalties, and other oil-linked payments. Overall, the results indicate that government tax revenues are resilient primarily to inflation but highly sensitive to external shocks, notably exchange rate movements and fluctuations in the global crude oil price. These findings highlight the importance of fiscal policies that stabilise currency, diversify revenue sources, and reduce dependence on oil.

Keywords: Tax revenue, Inflation, Exchange rate, Crude oil price, Fiscal performance

Introduction

Nigeria's tax revenue performance has been notably unimpressive, with the country heavily dependent on oil exports for government income. According to the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), tax revenue collection in Nigeria remains disproportionately low compared to other emerging economies (Rutto, 2020). Despite efforts to diversify the tax base and enhance collection mechanisms, the overall tax-to-GDP ratio stays below the African average, leaving the country vulnerable to external shocks, especially fluctuations in crude oil prices (Shivanda & Obwogi, 2018). Inflation and exchange rate volatility further worsen the situation by eroding the population's purchasing power and discouraging investment, thereby restricting the tax base. The literature on the link between price changes and government tax revenues in Nigeria remains limited, particularly concerning the combined effects of inflation, exchange rates, and crude oil prices on tax revenues relative to GDP. Existing studies mainly examine the individual impact of these price variables on the economy or provide sectoral analyses of tax revenues but lack a comprehensive view of how these price changes jointly influence government revenue performance (Nalyanya et al., 2020). The gap in research is further widened by the scarcity of empirical studies specifically focusing on Nigeria, despite its unique dependence on oil and the critical influence of exchange rate volatility and inflation on the economy. This study aims to address this gap by analysing the impact of price fluctuations—namely inflation, exchange rates, and crude oil prices—on government tax revenues as a percentage of GDP in Nigeria from 2000Q1 to 2023Q4. By exploring the interaction of these macroeconomic variables with tax revenues, the research strives to offer policymakers vital insights into how to refine tax policies and improve revenue collection strategies amid evolving economic conditions. Understanding this relationship is essential for developing a more resilient tax system that can withstand the volatility of both global and domestic economic forces.

Objectives of the Research

The overall aim of this study is to examine the impact of price changes on government tax revenues in Nigeria. However, the specific objectives include to:

- 1 Investigate the effect of inflation rates on government tax revenues in Nigeria.
- 2 Examine the impact of exchange rates on government tax revenues in Nigeria.
- 3 Ascertain the effect of crude oil prices on government tax revenues in Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

H01: Inflation rates do not significantly affect government tax revenues in Nigeria

H02: Exchange rates do not significantly affect government tax revenues in Nigeria

H03: Crude oil prices do not significantly influence government tax revenues in Nigeria

Review of Related Literature

Concept of tax revenues

Government tax revenues are the funds collected by the state from various types of taxes, which are essential for financing public goods and services. According to Abubakar and Akadiri (2022), government tax revenues encompass all income derived by the government from compulsory levies imposed on individuals, businesses, and other economic agents. Conversely, Babuga and Naseem (2022) define government tax revenues as the total revenue generated from taxes, including direct taxes such as income tax and indirect taxes like VAT. A third definition by Titus (2023) considers tax revenues as the government's primary source of funding for its budgetary expenditures and investments in development projects.

For this study, we adopt the definition provided by Babuga and Naseem (2022), which views government tax revenues as the total income generated from various tax instruments, including both direct and indirect taxes. This aligns with the broader understanding of tax revenues as a comprehensive measure of the government's fiscal capacity and its ability to fund public services and infrastructure. By including both income and consumption-based taxes, this definition captures the full spectrum of government tax collection, making it relevant for examining the impact of price changes on the government's fiscal health.

Different measures of government tax revenues exist, each offering unique insights into a country's fiscal health. One common measure is total tax revenue, which sums all forms of taxes collected within a given period. Another is the tax-to-GDP ratio, which compares tax revenue to the economy's total output (GDP). The tax-to-GDP ratio is a widely used indicator of a country's tax efficiency and its capacity to mobilise resources from its economy. Other measures include per capita tax revenue, which divides total tax revenue by the population, and the tax compliance rate, which assesses the proportion of taxes collected relative to taxes owed (Dauda et al., 2023).

The tax revenues to GDP ratio is the most suitable measure for this study, as it provides a clear understanding of how tax revenues relate to the size and performance of the overall economy. This measure is especially useful in assessing the government's capacity to generate revenue relative to its economic output, thus serving as an effective gauge of fiscal sustainability (Raifu, 2023). The tax-to-GDP ratio considers both structural and cyclical factors influencing tax collection, such as inflation, exchange rate fluctuations, and changes in crude oil prices, offering a comprehensive view of the economic environment in which tax revenues are generated. Furthermore, it enables comparisons across time and between countries, making it a robust measure for analysing the effect of price changes on government tax revenues in Nigeria.

Concept of price changes and their implication for government tax revenues

Price changes encompass fluctuations in the prices of goods and services within an economy or that are significant to an economy. According to Rutto (2020), price changes indicate the variation in the cost of goods and services over time, reflecting shifts in demand, supply, and other economic factors. In the context of inflation, price changes are viewed as increases in the general price level of goods and services (Obaretin & Akhor, 2019). Another definition by Nalyanya et al. (2020) highlights that price

changes result from various economic influences, including exchange rates, fiscal policies, and global price movements, which impact domestic price stability. A third perspective from Shivanda and Obwogi (2018) considers price changes arising from external shocks, such as fluctuations in oil prices, which directly affect the cost of living and economic equilibrium in oil-dependent economies like Nigeria.

For this study, we adopt the definition by Nalyanya et al. (2020), which regards price changes as the outcome of multiple interacting factors, such as inflation, exchange rates, and crude oil prices. This approach captures the complexity of price dynamics, especially in emerging economies like Nigeria, where external and domestic factors jointly influence price stability. Recognising price changes in this broader sense provides a more accurate understanding of how inflation, exchange rates, and crude oil prices impact the economy, particularly in relation to government tax revenues.

Price changes in Nigeria can be attributed to several key components: inflation, exchange rates, and crude oil prices. Inflation, defined as the general rise in prices over time, is a major driver of price fluctuations and affects consumers' purchasing power and government revenue (Raifu, 2023). Exchange rate variations influence the cost of imports and the value of the national currency, thereby impacting both inflation and the cost of living (Ihuarulam et al., 2021). Crude oil prices are particularly significant for Nigeria's economy, as changes in global oil prices directly influence government revenue from oil exports and can lead to adjustments in domestic prices, especially for energy-related goods and services (Babuga & Naseem, 2022). Collectively, these factors shape the overall price landscape within the Nigerian economy.

Theoretical Review

Laffer curve hypothesis

The Laffer Curve hypothesis was first proposed by economist Arthur Laffer in the 1970s, demonstrating the relationship between tax rates and government tax revenues. The theory indicates that there is an optimal tax rate that maximises revenue, and beyond a certain threshold, increasing tax rates can actually cause a reduction in revenue due to decreased incentives for work, investment, and production (Abubakar & Akadiri, 2022). The core assumption of the Laffer Curve is that at lower tax levels, tax rates and government revenue are positively correlated, but at higher rates, the incentive to engage in taxable activities diminishes, shrinking the overall tax base. The curve suggests that both under-taxation and over-taxation can lead to inefficiency and lower government income.

In this study's context, the Laffer Curve hypothesis can be employed to examine how variations in inflation, exchange rates, and crude oil prices affect Nigeria's tax revenues relative to GDP. As inflation increases or exchange rates fluctuate, the government might adjust tax rates to stabilise revenue. However, according to the Laffer Curve, excessively high tax rates could suppress economic activity, particularly in sectors heavily impacted by inflation and exchange rate volatility, such as manufacturing and agriculture (Babuga & Naseem, 2022). Furthermore, fluctuations in crude oil prices, a primary source of Nigeria's revenue, can significantly influence government revenue collection, requiring adjustments to tax policies. The Laffer Curve provides a framework for understanding the potential impact of these price variations on tax revenues in Nigeria, emphasising the importance of setting optimal tax rates that strike a balance between revenue generation and economic growth.

While the Laffer Curve offers valuable insights into the relationship between tax rates and revenue, its practical application has limitations. Firstly, the theory assumes a simplistic relationship, failing to account for the complexities of modern economies, where factors such as tax evasion, political influences, and external economic shocks play substantial roles in shaping government revenue (Obaretin & Akhor, 2019). In Nigeria, issues such as corruption, informal economic activities, and inefficient tax collection systems hinder the practical application of the Laffer Curve. Additionally, the hypothesis assumes a clear optimal tax rate, which may not exist in volatile economies where external factors, such as inflation or fluctuations in crude oil prices, continually influence tax bases and

government revenues (Dauda et al., 2023). Therefore, although the Laffer Curve provides a theoretical model, its limitations imply that more nuanced approaches are necessary to understand the complexities of tax revenue dynamics in Nigeria fully.

Review of Empirical Literature

Titus (2023) analysed the relationship between crude oil revenue and output growth in Nigeria from 2000 to 2019 using the Error Correction Model approach. The study was motivated by the disruptions to output growth and subsequent economic recessions caused by oil price shocks in Nigeria. The paper employed the Error Correction Model to estimate and analyse the impact of crude oil revenue on Nigeria's output growth. Descriptive analysis was used to present the data. The findings show that all variables except net foreign assets had positive but mostly insignificant effects on GDP. Net foreign assets showed a negative and statistically insignificant impact on GDP growth.

Raifu (2023) empirically examined the effect of oil revenue on economic growth in Nigeria using the Quantile Regression method from 1981 to 2018. To achieve this objective, the study adopts a quantile regression approach. For robustness, the results from the quantile regression are compared with those from OLS estimation. The OLS results indicate that oil revenue has a positive and statistically significant impact on economic growth. However, when controlling for other determinants of economic growth, such as human capital, investment, and trade openness, the Quantile Regression shows that oil revenue has a less significant effect on the economy. This study further finds that human capital and investment stimulate economic growth, while trade openness appears not to have any significant effect across the quantiles.

Dauda et al. (2023) assessed the relationship between oil revenue and sustainable economic growth in Nigeria from 1981 to 2021. The study adopted the Johansen co-integration test and the associated error correction mechanism (ECM) to analyse data sourced from both the World Development Indicators and the Nigerian Central Bank. The findings revealed that oil revenue significantly boosts economic growth in Nigeria, while the Granger causality results showed a bidirectional causality between oil revenue and economic growth in Nigeria.

Ebimobowei (2022) empirically examined the relationship between oil revenue and Nigeria's economic growth from 1990 to 2019. The study adopted an ex post facto research approach, and secondary data for the investigation were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin, the Federal Inland Revenue Service Fact Book, and the World Bank Development Website. The study employed Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) multiple regression analysis. The results indicated that crude oil and gas exports have a significant and negative relationship with Nigeria's real gross domestic product. At the same time, petroleum profit tax and royalties demonstrated a significant and positive relationship. Additionally, both domestic crude oil sales and oil licensing fees showed significant relationships with Nigeria's real gross domestic product.

Ikue et al. (2022) empirically examined the relationship between economic growth and crude oil revenue in Nigeria, controlling for industrial shocks from 1980 to 2019. The variables were taken from the World Bank's World Development Indicators (WDI), OPEC Statistics, Baker Hughes Rig Count, and the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin. Using the ARDL approach, the study demonstrates that oil income can contribute to Nigeria's economic growth while also protecting the environment during exploration.

Odido et al. (2023) shifted their focus in the study to determining the effects of crude oil price fluctuations on the growth rate of the Nigerian economy. Adopting an ex-post facto research design with data covering the period from 1997 to 2022, the study found that there is no significant relationship between crude oil price fluctuations and the growth rate of the Nigerian economy. The results suggested a potential imbalance arising from the effects of crude oil exports and refined oil imports. Recommendations included diversifying the economy into sectors like manufacturing, agriculture, and tourism to reduce dependence on the oil sector.

Gbadamosi et al. (2022) examined the impact of four key variables (crude oil price, real exchange rate, inflation, and population) on Nigeria's economic growth. The study utilised annual time series data obtained from the World Development Indicator (WDI). Johansen Co-integration test and Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) were conducted to determine the co-integrating relationships among the variables. The findings clearly showed that crude oil price, real exchange rate, inflation, and population all significantly affected the response variable (GDP) in both the short and long term. The rise and fall in crude oil prices have negatively impacted Nigeria's economic growth and real exchange rate and have also contributed to inflationary increases in the country over time.

Abubakar and Akadiri (2022) examined the influence of oil rents and revenues on Nigeria's economic growth. They utilised Novel dynamic ARDL simulation and Kernel Regularised Least Squares (KRLS) with annual time series data from 1973 to 2020. The results indicate that oil rents are negligible and have diminishing marginal effects on Nigeria's economic growth. However, oil revenue has a significant and sustainable impact on Nigeria's economic growth.

Babuga and Naseem (2022) investigate the effect of oil price fluctuations on economic growth in African oil-exporting countries, employing the Pooled Mean Group (PMG) and Mean Group (MG) methods. They found that an increase in oil prices promotes economic growth in the sample countries. They also discovered that oil price influences economic growth at a specific threshold; beyond this point, the effect becomes negative.

Atolagbe and Abiodun (2021) examined the impact of trade liberalisation and six macroeconomic variables on tax revenue in Nigeria for the period 1981-2019, using the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) approach to co-integration and the Error Correction Model (ECM). The unrestricted error-correction model was specified in the study by modifying the ARDL model. Total tax and domestic tax revenues were predicted by trade liberalisation and most macroeconomic variables investigated. A unit increase in trade liberalisation triggered a 3% rise in both total and domestic tax revenues when all other variables in the model were held constant. The ECM results showed that both long-run and short-run equilibria were present in the system. The macroeconomic variables identified as predictors of both domestic and external tax revenues are the share of petroleum and mining in GDP, foreign direct investment, the share of agriculture in GDP, per capita income, exchange rate, and inflation rate. These are therefore important for explaining tax revenue in Nigeria.

Ihwarulam et al. (2021) examined the relationship between tax revenue and selected macroeconomic variables. Panel data analysis was applied to data from six ECOWAS countries, encompassing tax revenue, inflation, gross domestic product, trade openness, unemployment, and exchange rates over the period 2005-2019. The Wald's test and Hausman test indicated that a fixed effects regression was suitable for the study. The results showed that inflation was positively associated with tax revenue and was statistically significant at the 5% level. A unit increase in inflation led to a 0.007 increase in the tax revenue measure; economic growth was also positive and statistically significant at 5 per cent; a rising GDP resulted in a 0.78 increase in government tax revenue.

Obaretin and Akhor (2019) examined the role of taxation as a tool for tackling inflationary challenges in Nigeria. Data were collected from the Annual Abstract of the Office of the National Bureau of Statistics and the Federal Inland Revenue Service over a span of twenty years (1994 to 2014). The data were analysed using the error correction model (ECM), and the analysis revealed that all the variables—company's income tax, value-added tax, and customs and excise duties—had a positive but non-significant relationship with inflation.

Rutto (2020) examines the impact of the exchange rate on tax revenue performance in Kenya. The study utilised annual time series secondary data from 2003 to 2018 to estimate a linear model of tax revenue performance and the selected macroeconomic factor. The data were collected from the Central Bank of Kenya, Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (KNBS), Ministry of Finance's data on National Budgets, and other Government records. The study adopted a correlation and regression analysis research design. The findings revealed that exchange rates had a negative relationship with tax revenue collection.

Nalyanya et al. (2020) examined the effects of macroeconomic variables on tax revenue performance in Kenya using annual time series data from ten years, covering the period 2008 to 2018. The study employed a correlation research design, which is a non-experimental research technique. The study found a negative relationship between inflation and tax revenue performance.

Omotosho (2019) examines the macroeconomic effects of oil price shocks and the current fuel subsidy regime in Nigeria. To achieve this, we develop and estimate a New-Keynesian DSGE model that captures the pass-through effect of international oil prices into retail fuel prices. Our findings reveal that oil price shocks cause significant and lasting impacts on output, contributing around 22 percent of its fluctuations up to the fourth year. In our benchmark model (i.e., with fuel subsidies), we demonstrate that a negative oil price shock reduces overall GDP, increases non-oil GDP, raises headline inflation, and leads to currency depreciation. Conversely, results from the model without fuel subsidies suggest that the contractionary impact of a negative oil price shock on aggregate GDP is lessened, headline inflation falls, and the exchange rate depreciates more in the short term.

Ofori et al. (2018) examined the relationship between exchange rate volatility and tax revenue in Ghana. To estimate the impact of exchange rate volatility on tax revenue, the study employed the Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique after generating annual exchange rate volatilities using the GARCH (1,1) method. The study's results suggest that exchange rate volatility adversely affects tax revenue both in the short and long term, with the effect being more pronounced in the long term.

Kalas et al. (2018) examined the relationship between the inflation rate and the value-added tax rate in seven countries in the region from 2008 to 2016. The selected countries are Serbia, Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Macedonia, Montenegro, and Slovenia. Based on the graph, it was observed that during years when the value-added tax increased, the inflation rate decreased, indicating there is no positive effect of the tax type on inflation, but rather a reduction in the inflation rate. Additionally, considering that the inflation rate is not mainly caused by changes in the value-added tax rate, the authors focused on analysing the differences between the average inflation rates in the observed countries.

Odunsi et al. (2018) investigated the impact of macroeconomic variables on tax revenue performance in Nigeria from 1987 to 2016. The study considered 1987 as the baseline, with data sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria and other federal institutions. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) was employed for the estimation. Pre- and post-diagnostic tests were conducted before the analysis. The Adjusted R² indicates that the explanatory variables account for about 95% of all the variations in the dependent variable. The p-value and F-statistics were statistically significant at 1% (0.000), implying that the explanatory variables collectively influence tax revenue performance. Overall, the results reveal a significantly positive effect of exchange rate and real gross domestic product on tax revenue performance, whereas the inflation rate had a negative, but insignificant, effect within the timeframe.

Ali and Audi (2018) examined the macroeconomic environment and tax revenue in Pakistan, analysing the impact of macroeconomic factors on tax revenues in Pakistan from 1975 to 2016. They found that unemployment had a positive and significant impact on tax revenue, while money supply was also positively and significantly related to tax revenue. Conversely, inflation had a negative and significant effect on tax revenue. These findings indicated that the macroeconomic environment was healthy, which further supported an increase in tax revenue.

Shivanda and Obwogi (2018) examined the impact of macroeconomic variables on tax revenue in Kenya. Their analysis used a dataset from 1995 to 2016 with ANOVA. Their results, among other findings, showed that there is no statistically significant link between interest rate, inflation, and exchange rate and tax revenue; however, interest rate and exchange rate were key in predicting tax revenues. The overall conclusion was that interest rate and exchange rate are significant macroeconomic factors affecting tax revenue collection in Kenya.

The study conducted by Onakoya et al. (2017) used data from 2005 to 2014 to examine the significant relationship between tax revenue performance, trade liberalisation, and macroeconomic variables in 22

sub-Saharan African countries. Several tests were performed, and the Vector Error Correction Model was employed to explore potential long- or short-term associations among the variables. The Granger causality test was used to assess the impact of one variable on another. The findings indicated that inflation, interest rates, and trade openness had a short-term relationship with tax revenue, unlike exchange rate and unemployment. All variables, except exchange rate, were positively related to the dependent variable, and there was evidence of one-way causation without serial correlation or heteroskedasticity among the variables.

Anichebe (2015) examined the implication of tax policy on inflation in Nigeria. The study period covered from 1981 to 2012 (32 years), and relevant data for the study were gathered from the Central Bank of Nigeria's annual reports. Subsequently, a combination of the Johansen test, ordinary least squares (OLS), and Granger causality/Block exogeneity Wald test was conducted. The findings of the study revealed that a long-run relationship exists between tax policy and inflation in Nigeria, emphasising that the personal income tax rate has a negative effect on inflation during the reviewed period. Meanwhile, company income tax, property tax, and consumption tax exerted a significant positive impact on inflation.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employs an ex post facto research design to investigate the impact of price changes, specifically inflation, exchange rates, and crude oil prices, on government tax revenues (measured as tax revenues as a percentage of GDP) in Nigeria from 2000Q1 to 2023Q4. The research employs a time-series approach, which is suitable for examining relationships between economic variables over a specified period. The design facilitates the analysis of temporal dynamics and provides insight into how variations in inflation, exchange rates, and crude oil prices affect the government's tax revenue generation in Nigeria.

The population of this study encompasses all macroeconomic variables and the tax revenue-to-GDP ratio in Nigeria from 2000Q1 to 2023Q4. This period is chosen to encompass the full range of macroeconomic fluctuations, policy changes, and oil price volatility that Nigeria has experienced in recent decades. The data is collected from official sources, including the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC), and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). The sample for this study is based on the quarterly data available for the period from 2000Q1 to 2023Q4. Since the study focuses solely on Nigeria, the sample consists of 94 quarterly observations (i.e., 94 data points).

Model Specification

The model of the study will be a modification and composition of the models of Odido et al. (2023), Gbadamosi et al. (2022), Abubakar and Akadiri (2022), and Babuga and Naseem (2022) for macroeconomic variables affecting the government sector and the economy. Using their models, this study's model is specified as:

$$GTXR_t = \pi_0 + \rho_1 INF_t + \rho_2 EXR_t + \rho_3 CRP_t + \mu_t \quad 1$$

Where,

- GTXR = government tax revenues at time t.
- INF = inflation rates
- EXR = exchange rates
- CRP = crude oil prices
- μ_t = the error term,
- π_0 = intercept
- $\pi_1 - \pi_4$ = short-run coefficients to be estimated,

- $\rho_1 - \rho_4 =$ long-run coefficients to be estimated

Methods of Data Analysis

Data analysis for this study is carried out using the Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) estimation technique. FMOLS is appropriate for analysing long-term relationships between factors such as inflation, exchange rates, crude oil prices, and government revenues, when cointegration is present. This method adjusts for both serial correlation and endogeneity in the regressors, delivering unbiased and efficient estimates of long-run parameters (Phillips & Hansen, 1990).

Data Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation

Descriptive Statistics Results

The descriptive statistics of government tax revenues (GTXR), exchange rates (EXR), crude oil prices (CRP), and inflation rates (INF) reveal notable patterns in their distribution and variability. Government tax revenues had a mean of 1.16 and a standard deviation of 0.23, indicating moderate variation around the average. The positive skewness of 2.13 and high kurtosis of 7.72 suggest that GTXR is heavily right-skewed with extreme high values, which is further confirmed by the significant Jarque-Bera test ($p = 0.000$), implying non-normality. Exchange rates exhibited the highest volatility, with a mean of 236.20 and a standard deviation of 178.87, along with extreme right-skewness (2.74) and kurtosis (12.19), highlighting the presence of substantial outliers and sharp deviations from normality. In contrast, crude oil prices were relatively stable, with a mean of 63.18 and lower skewness (0.06), although the Jarque-Bera test ($p = 0.043$) indicates a mild departure from normality. Inflation rates had a mean of 13.13 and a standard deviation of 4.49, showing moderate dispersion; its slight positive skew (0.51) and kurtosis near 3 suggest a distribution close to normal, which aligns with the non-significant Jarque-Bera probability ($p = 0.07$).

Table 1: Descriptive statistics

	GTXR	EXR	CRP	INF
Mean	1.160353	236.1967	63.18083	13.12700
Median	1.047022	157.2038	61.67125	12.71156
Maximum	2.168553	1155.606	102.3522	27.69625
Minimum	0.952442	106.9266	25.33844	4.896071
Std. Dev.	0.229492	178.8683	24.37445	4.492712
Skewness	2.126737	2.737195	0.056862	0.512624
Kurtosis	7.721384	12.19231	1.752995	3.527048
Jarque-Bera	161.5341	457.8702	6.271816	5.315647
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.043460	0.070101
Sum	111.3939	22674.88	6065.360	1260.192
Sum Sq. Dev.	5.003346	3039418.	56440.79	1917.524
Observations	96	96	96	96

The range and variability in the data also reveal important economic insights. Government tax revenues fluctuated between 0.95 and 2.17, reflecting periods of low and high revenue mobilization. Exchange rates varied dramatically from 106.93 to 1155.61, indicating episodes of significant currency

depreciation and instability. Crude oil prices spanned 25.34 to 102.35, highlighting sensitivity to global oil market conditions, while inflation rates ranged from 4.90 to 27.70, signalling episodes of both moderate and high inflationary pressure in the economy. The high skewness and kurtosis values for GTXR and EXR indicate that both variables are prone to extreme observations, which may affect fiscal and monetary policy responses. Meanwhile, the relative stability of CRP and INF suggests these variables could have more predictable effects on government revenues and economic planning over time.

Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

H01: Inflation rates do not significantly affect government tax revenues in Nigeria

Decision Criteria: If, $p\text{-value} < 0.05$, then the variable is significant: **Reject H_0**
 $p\text{-value} > 0.05$, then variable is not significant: **Accept H_0**

Table 2: Test of Hypothesis One

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.	Decision
INF	0.0113	0.0071	1.5980	0.1135	Accept H01

The results of the test of Hypothesis One indicate that inflation rates (INF) do not have a statistically significant effect on government tax revenues (GTXR) in Nigeria. The estimated coefficient of 0.0113 suggests a positive relationship, implying that higher inflation is associated with a slight increase in tax revenues; however, the effect is not statistically significant, as the p-value of 0.1135 exceeds the 5% significance threshold. Consequently, the null hypothesis (H01) is accepted, indicating that variations in inflation rates do not meaningfully influence government tax revenue during the period under study.

Test of Hypothesis Two

H02: Exchange rates do not significantly affect government tax revenues in Nigeria

Decision Criteria: If $p\text{-value} < 0.05$, then the variable is significant: **Reject H_0**
 $p\text{-value} > 0.05$, then variable is not significant: **Accept H_0**

Table 3: Test of Hypothesis Two

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.	Decision
EXR	0.0007	0.0002	4.0050	0.0001	Reject H02

The results of the test of Hypothesis Two indicate that exchange rates (EXR) have a statistically significant effect on government tax revenues (GTXR) in Nigeria. The coefficient of 0.0007 is positive, suggesting that depreciation in the exchange rate is associated with an increase in government tax revenues. The p-value of 0.0001 is well below the 5% significance level, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H02).

Test of Hypothesis Three

H03: Crude oil prices do not significantly influence government tax revenues in Nigeria

Decision Criteria: If $p\text{-value} < 0.05$, then the variable is significant: **Reject H_0**

p-value > 0.05, then variable is not significant: **Accept H_0**

Table 3: Test of Hypothesis Three

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.	Decision
CRP	0.0034	0.0010	3.4270	0.0009	Reject H03

The results of the test of Hypothesis Three indicate that crude oil prices (CRP) have a statistically significant effect on government tax revenues (GTXR) in Nigeria. The estimated coefficient of 0.0034 is positive, suggesting that increases in crude oil prices are associated with higher government tax revenues. The p-value of 0.0009 is well below the 5% significance threshold, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0).

Discussion of Findings

The main aim of the study is to examine the effects of price changes on government tax revenues in Nigeria. To achieve this, three operational objectives were selected, and three hypotheses were formulated and tested in earlier sections. Based on the results of hypothesis testing, the following discussions are presented.

Effects of Inflation rates on government tax revenues in Nigeria

The finding indicates that variations in inflation rates do not significantly influence government tax revenue during the period under study. This suggests that other macroeconomic factors, such as exchange rate fluctuations or crude oil price changes, may play a more important role in determining government tax revenues than inflation alone. While inflation may have some nominal effect on revenues, it does not exert a notable statistical impact, highlighting the relative stability of tax collections against short-term inflationary pressures in the Nigerian context. The result that variations in inflation rates do not notably influence government tax revenue during the study period aligns with empirical evidence suggesting that certain macroeconomic variables may have limited or context-specific effects on fiscal outcomes. Titus (2023) found that most variables, including net foreign assets, had positive but largely insignificant impacts on GDP in Nigeria, indicating that fluctuations in key economic indicators do not automatically lead to meaningful changes in aggregate economic or fiscal performance. This supports the current finding, implying that inflationary movements alone may not substantially alter government revenue, especially in an economy where other structural factors, such as oil revenue dependence and administrative capacity, dominate.

Similarly, Raifu (2023) showed that controlling for factors like human capital and investment reduced the apparent impact of oil revenue on economic growth, indicating that underlying determinants and sectoral dynamics can lessen the influence of nominal macroeconomic variables, such as inflation, on outcomes like government revenue. Ebimobowei (2022) also highlighted that while some oil-related revenues, such as petroleum profit taxes, significantly affect GDP, other streams, including domestic crude sales, have no meaningful effect, reinforcing the idea that not all economic fluctuations equally influence fiscal performance. Dauda et al. (2023), although reporting significant links between oil revenue and growth, emphasise the importance of structural and policy factors in mediating economic outcomes. Collectively, these studies support the conclusion that variations in inflation rates may not significantly drive changes in government tax revenue in Nigeria, given the dominance of other, more influential determinants.

Effects of exchange rates on government tax revenues in Nigeria

This outcome emphasises the sensitivity of government tax revenues to exchange rate movements, likely because currency depreciation increases the local currency value of traded goods, imports, and export-related earnings, which in turn raises taxable income and customs duties. Therefore, exchange rate fluctuations appear to play a significant role in shaping Nigeria's fiscal revenue performance. The finding that government tax revenues are sensitive to exchange rate movements is supported by studies linking currency fluctuations to economic and fiscal performance in Nigeria. Ebimobwei (2022) highlighted that certain oil-related revenues, such as petroleum profit taxes, significantly influence GDP, suggesting that sectors exposed to international trade and foreign currency transactions respond strongly to exchange rate changes. This aligns with the notion that currency depreciation can raise the local currency value of exports and imports, thereby increasing taxable income and customs duties. Similarly, Gbadamosi et al. (2022) found that the real exchange rate significantly affects Nigeria's GDP in both the short and long run, reinforcing the idea that fiscal outcomes are sensitive to currency movements, as they directly influence trade-related revenues and the domestic valuation of foreign income.

Additional evidence comes from Ikue et al. (2022), who observed that oil income contributes to economic growth while being closely linked to external market conditions, suggesting that exchange rate dynamics can magnify the fiscal effects of traded goods and oil-related revenue. Although Odido et al. (2023) found that fluctuations in crude oil prices did not directly significantly influence growth rates, their results underscored the imbalance caused by reliance on oil exports and imports, further indicating that currency movements indirectly impact government revenue through trade channels. Collectively, these studies support the conclusion that exchange rate variations play a vital role in shaping government tax revenues, mainly through their effect on the local currency valuation of traded goods, exports, and import-related earnings.

Effects of crude oil prices on government tax revenues in Nigeria

This finding suggests that government tax revenues in Nigeria are highly sensitive to fluctuations in crude oil prices, reflecting the country's significant reliance on oil-related earnings for fiscal revenue. Rising crude oil prices likely enhance revenue through higher corporate taxes, royalties, and other oil-linked fiscal inflows, while declines in oil prices could pose risks to government revenue mobilisation. The finding that government tax revenues in Nigeria are sensitive to fluctuations in crude oil prices is consistent with evidence highlighting the centrality of oil-related earnings to fiscal performance. Abubakar and Akadiri (2022) reported that while oil rents alone have limited effects on economic growth, oil revenue has a significant and sustainable impact, reflecting the government's reliance on oil earnings. Similarly, Babuga and Naseem (2022) found that increases in oil prices generally enhance economic growth in African oil-exporting countries, although beyond certain thresholds, the effect can turn negative. This highlights the significance of oil price fluctuations for fiscal stability, as they directly impact government revenue streams derived from petroleum-related activities.

Further support comes from Atolagbe and Abiodun (2021), who identified petroleum's share in GDP as a key predictor of both domestic and total tax revenues in Nigeria, indicating that oil-dependent revenues respond strongly to changes in global crude prices. Ihuarulam et al. (2021) also emphasised that macroeconomic variables, including trade-related income and economic growth, significantly determine tax revenue, which indirectly links oil price movements to fiscal outcomes, given Nigeria's reliance on oil exports for GDP and trade receipts. Collectively, these studies reinforce the finding that government tax revenues in Nigeria are highly sensitive to fluctuations in the crude oil price, highlighting the fiscal vulnerability associated with dependence on the oil sector.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study analysed the effects of price changes, specifically inflation rates, exchange rates, and crude oil prices, on government tax revenues in Nigeria. The findings indicate that fluctuations in inflation rates do not significantly influence tax revenue, suggesting that other macroeconomic factors, such as exchange rate movements and oil price swings, have a greater impact on fiscal outcomes. Conversely, exchange rate fluctuations were found to significantly affect government tax revenues, reflecting how currency depreciation impacts the local valuation of traded goods, exports, and imports, which directly influences taxable income and customs duties. Likewise, changes in crude oil prices had a substantial effect on tax revenues, underscoring Nigeria's reliance on oil-related income for fiscal stability. Overall, the results suggest that government tax revenue in Nigeria remains largely resilient to short-term inflationary pressures but is highly susceptible to external price shocks, particularly exchange rate shifts and global crude oil price variations, highlighting the fiscal vulnerability linked to oil dependence and trade exposure.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are proposed: First, since inflation does not significantly impact tax revenue, fiscal authorities should focus less on short-term inflation control as a revenue strategy and instead prioritise structural reforms that boost tax administration, expand the tax base, and enhance compliance.

Second, because tax revenues are sensitive to movements in the exchange rate, government policies should focus on stabilising the currency and managing external trade exposure. Measures such as hedging foreign currency risks, encouraging export diversification, and monitoring import valuation can help optimise revenue collection related to trade and foreign currency transactions.

Third, since crude oil prices greatly influence government tax revenues, policymakers should formulate strategies to lessen fiscal dependence on oil. This may include broadening non-oil revenue sources, investing in alternative sectors, and creating stabilisation funds to counteract revenue fluctuations, thereby ensuring a more stable and sustainable fiscal performance amidst volatile oil markets.

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